

SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS IN THE COURSE OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK

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Abstract: *In this article, we will discuss the basic principles and principles of social and educational work in today's public life, the spiritual and educational work, and religious extremism, international terrorism, anti-terrorism, anti-terrorism, anti-terrorism, anti-government, anti-government, anti-terrorism, anti-terrorism, anti-terrorism.*

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Indeed, today's dangerous period requires a constant increase in the effectiveness of the propaganda of national ideas and spiritual and educational work. Because in order to achieve our ultimate goal, we need to prevent any unpleasant actions and problems, given how fast and rapid times are changing.

To do this, it is necessary to find such forms of spiritual-enlightenment work, with the help of which it is possible to have an educational effect on society and on each individual at the same time and with the same force. This encourages us to constantly study and effectively use the national and foreign experience of spiritual and educational work.

Among the main principles that determine the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work are the national ideological orientation, the unity of education and upbringing, the unity of vitality, integrity, consciousness and behavior; practicality, publicity, encouragement of student initiative, creative cooperation, mutual respect, mutual encouragement, enlightenment struggle against the influence of "mass culture", coherence of influence of factors of membership, ideological and artistic upbringing. At the same time, some of our intellectuals, even scientists, are calling for either indifference or liberal attitude to the phenomenon of "mass culture." An example of this is a speech by Doctor of Philosophy V. Alimasov. "The 'mass culture' used in the West corresponds to the 'folk culture' we use," he said. But Bogomil Raynov, a

well-known Bulgarian scholar who studied "popular culture" 50 years ago, refutes this idea in his fundamental work, "Popular Culture." "Popular culture," he said, "completely denies, first and foremost, the populism of culture."

Propaganda (Arabic: interest, dissemination) - in a broad sense, is a special type of social activity, the promotion of scientific, artistic, socio-political, national ideas and values in order to increase the socio-political activity of the population. In the process of propaganda, the achievements of science, art, politics and ideology are widely disseminated, enriched and further developed. 2) activity in the narrow sense, aimed at promoting ideology and policy. Propaganda should be based on the principles of science, specificity, objectivity, and close connection with social life, and should be organized. Propaganda (Lat. Propaganda - information to be disseminated) - an activity aimed at popularizing certain ideas in the public consciousness through word of mouth or the media.

Propaganda - (Arabic: passion), (Latin agitation - to mobilize) - a propaganda activity that encourages a particular social group or community to be active towards the intended goal. There are oral, printed and audio, video forms of propaganda, which is a very effective means of socio-political struggle. At all times and in all places, in any country that cares about the future of its people, the population has been informed about the policies, reforms and changes pursued by the state. This serves the purpose of uniting the society, ensuring the mobilization of the nation and achieving the unity of the state and society. Propaganda also includes encouragement in written and oral forms in order to influence people, thereby arousing pleasure, love, or hatred in their hearts.

Even now, the ideas of religious extremism, international terrorism, egocentrism, statelessness, and immorality are being propagated, armed with new 21st century technologies. Although the means, forms, and goals are changing, being called by different names, they are rooted in the propaganda of certain ideas. That is why we call such propaganda, which is aimed at disturbing the peace of others, impeding sustainable development, and against national interests, destructive propaganda.

Based on the results and recommendations of this study, in June 2018, the "Scientific and Methodological Support Department" of the Republican Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment began to prepare propaganda slides and infographics for the Republican system of spirituality and enlightenment. To date, the center has developed and implemented more than 100 methodological media products.

Methodologically, the interaction between the facilitator and the listener

will consist of two types of interactions. The first type of impact is that at a certain stage of the event, the listener is given guiding questions to help them understand the issue at that stage. The second is to show the way of thinking and actions that define the problem. The number of questions and instructions is determined by the participants' mastery of the presentation materials.

Incentives. Establishing an award to encourage active participants gives good results. At the same time, the participants develop a positive spirit of debate, competition, which increases the effectiveness of the event, stimulates the audience to participate in future events.

Adequate presentation method. The name of the event should be interesting, simple, clear, engaging, dedicated to a topical issue that corresponds to the age, profession, interests of the participants, is one of the tasks of spiritual, ideological, educational work. In naming the event, it is far from too formal, too scientific, too long; sentences should be avoided. Because formality bores people from the event. It is more effective to use words that are used more in our daily lives when naming a topic. The name of the event should be interesting and inspiring. Anyone who has heard or read the topic should understand what to think about at the event and have a sense of belonging to the problem. Therefore, it is necessary to inform the participants of the most important points in the announcement of the event.

The method of adapting to the audience. The age and professionalism of the participants should be taken into account when giving examples during the event. If the majority of participants are young people, examples from the recent past, events and situations that young people are not indifferent to and directly witnessed by the generation participating in the event will be cited during the event. If the participants are middle-aged, the examples given are taken from the realities witnessed by the middle generation, from the news happening around us. At the same time, participants will be able to choose examples based on their profession. Communication efficiency increases when participants select examples that they see every day.

There are similarities between the field of social medicine and upbringing, spirituality and enlightenment, and therefore the need to establish a diagnosis of "Which neighborhood has the most mental patients?" And an alternative work program for each district and neighborhood ;

When the thousands of events held were effective, there would be no crime, no rulings, no indifference. Therefore, it is necessary to check the results of the ongoing spiritual and educational work;

nationalization of the book trade, cessation of the publication of light-weight books developed in the handicraft style;

He warned that language, culture, and customs were being violated, and that society was becoming accustomed to our "mass culture."

Doctor of Philosophy, Professor F. Turgunbaev said that instead of watching the information channel "Akhborot" during prime time on the country's TV channels, people watch various light TV series, which negatively affects the reforms in the country, the promotion of spiritual and educational information that every citizen should know. and suggestions on the need to regulate this issue.

The issues to be communicated to the participants at the beginning of the event will be given to all participants in the form of questions. The initial result is recorded. At the end of the event, the same questions will be asked again. Compared to the previous result, the efficiency is determined. Then the opinion of the people who respond plays the role of repetitive propaganda.

The script written for the event should be designed taking into account the characteristics of the speaker, such as experience, level of knowledge. The main criterion is the personal training of the speaker on the topic. Therefore, each speaker is either socially or economically well-informed when writing a script for an event. it should rely more on either the political or the legal sphere. This will ensure a reliable presentation of the report. After the event, participants will have a clear system of knowledge.

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